

Global Warming Datasets 1-2024

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Abstract

This work describes the global warming datasets in the period 1-2024.

The data for the period 1-1850 are from paleoclimate records and are used for determination of global warming in the last 2,000 years.

The data for the 1850-2024 period are based on directly measured records.

This work extends also the lower limit of the global warming over land and global warming over the ocean datasets from 1850 to 1750.

The original data are according to various baselines and were converted in this work to the uniform “preindustrial” 1850-1900 baseline.

The final dataset of global warming in the 1-2024 period based on this work is available on the site nowagreen.com.

Glossary

Amp	amplitude of data around trendline, °C
Ave	Average, °C
BL	baseline of Global Warming data
CF	Conversion Factor across baselines, °C
CF(pBL)	conversion Factor to 1850-1900 preindustrial baseline, °C
GW	Global Warming, global surface temperature of land+ocean, °C above the 1850-1900 baseline
GWL	global surface temperature over land only, °C above the 1850-1900 baseline
GWO	global surface temperature over the ocean only, °C above the 1850-1900 baseline
miniAmp	dataset with reduced amplitude
Paleo	Global Warming dataset based on paleoclimate records in the last 2,000 years [1] [2]
pBL	global warming data above 1850-1900 preindustrial period baseline
Ref	reference
Thermo	thermal measurements for determination of global warming using thermometers and satellites (after 1750)
TL	trendline

Global Warming Baseline and Units

All results of calculations in this work are in °C above the preindustrial 1850-1900 baseline (pBL).

Datasets Conversion to the Preindustrial Baseline 1850-1900

Most datasets include the 1850-1900 period which allows direct determination of the conversion factor for each dataset.

NASA dataset starts after 1850 and cannot be directly converted to the 1850-1900 baseline. The NASA dataset is above the 1951-1980 baseline.

The NASA conversion factor will be determined using the averages of the 1951-1980 period of other converted datasets.

Table 1 - Global Warming GW (Land+Ocean) Datasets

Table 2 - Global Warming GW (Land+Ocean) datasets considered in this work

	Ref	ID	1-1850	1850-1880	1880-1950	1950-2000	2000-2014	2014-2024
Paleo	[1] [2]	DB11						
Thermo	[1] [2]	DB12						
NASA	[3] [4]	DB13						
NOAA	[5]	DB14						
LBL	[6] [7]	DB15						
IPCC	[8]	DB16						
Ave	*	DB17						

* this publication

Paleo Database (DB11) 1-2000 for GW (Land+Ocean)

This dataset is based on paleoclimatology.

Paleoclimate

From IPCC [1] wg1, Section 6.2.1.2 and 6.2.1.3:

"Perhaps one of the most important aspects of modern palaeoclimatology is that it is possible to derive time series of atmospheric trace gases and aerosols for the period from about 650 kyr to the present from air trapped in polar ice and from the ice itself."

“Tree ring records are generally the most accurate, and are accurate to the year, or season of a year (even back thousands of years). There are a host of other proxies that also have annual layers or bands (e.g., corals, varved sediments, some cave deposits, some ice cores) but the age models associated with these are not always exact to a specific year.”

“There continue to be significant advances in radiometric dating. Each radiometric system has ranges over which the system is useful, and palaeoclimatic studies almost always publish analytical uncertainties. Because there can be additional uncertainties, methods have been developed for checking assumptions and cross verifying with independent methods. For example, secular variations in the radiocarbon clock over the last 12 kyr are well known, and fairly well understood over the last 35 kyr. These variations, and the quality of the radiocarbon clock, have both been well demonstrated via comparisons with age models derived from precise tree ring and varved sediment records, as well as with age determinations derived from independent radiometric systems such as uranium series.”

Table 3 - DB11 - Paleo Database info [1] [2]

DB11	Paleo
Name	Paleo
ID	DB11
Reference	[1] [2]
Units	°C
Records	annual
From	1
To	2000
Years	2,000
Baseline (BL)	1961-1990
BL years	30
Ave in BL	-0.0008
Decimal places	4
CF(pBL)	+0.3794

Chart 1 - DB11 - Paleo dataset - Global Warming (Land +Ocean) 1-2000, °C
above pBL [1] [2]

Thermo Database (DB12) 1850-2017 for GW (Land+Ocean)

Table 4 - DB12 - Thermo Database info [1] [2]

DB12	Thermo
Name	Thermo
ID	DB12
Reference	[1] [2]
Units	°C
Records	annual
From	1850
To	2017
Years	168
Baseline (BL)	1961-1990
BL years	30
Ave in BL	0.0000
Decimal places	4
CF(pBL)	+0.3536

Chart 2 - DB12 - Thermo dataset - Global Warming (Land+Ocean) 1850-2017, °C above pBL [1] [2]

NASA Database (DB13) 1880-2024 for GW (Land+Ocean)Table 5 - DB13 - NASA Database info [3] [4]

DB13	NASA
Name	NASA
ID	DB13
Reference	[3] [4]
Units	°C
Records	annual
From	1880
To	2024
Years	145
Baseline (BL)	1951-1980
BL years	30
Ave in BL	-0.0003
Decimal places	2
CF(pBL)	+0.2807

Chart 3 - DB13 - NASA dataset - Global Warming (Land+Ocean) 1880-2024, °C above pBL [3] [4]

NOAA Database (DB14) 1850-2024 for GW (Land+Ocean)

Table 6 - DB14 - NOAA Database info [5]

DB14	NOAA
Name	NOAA
ID	DB14
Reference	[5]
Units	°C
Records	annual
From	1850
To	2024
Years	175
Baseline (BL)	1901-2000
BL years	100
Ave in BL	+0.0002
Decimal places	2
CF(pBL)	+0.1704

Chart 4 - DB14 - NOAA dataset - Global Warming (Land+Ocean) 1850-2024, °C above pBL [5]

Berkley Earth (LBL) Database (DB15) 1850-2024 for GW (Land+Ocean)

Table 7 - DB15 - LBL Database info [6] [7]

DB15	Berkley Earth
Name	LBL
ID	DB15
Reference	[6] [7]
Units	°C
Records	annual
From	1850
To	2024
Years	175
Baseline (BL)	1951-1980
BL years	30
Ave in BL	+0.0174
Decimal places	3
CF(pBL)	+0.3062

Chart 5 - DB15 – Berkley Earth (LBL) dataset - Global Warming (Land+Ocean) 1850-2024, °C above pBL [6] [7]

IPCC Database (DB16) 1950-2014 for GW (Land+Ocean)

Table 8 - DB16 - IPCC Database info [8]

DB16	IPCC
Name	IPCC
ID	DB16
Reference	[8]
Units	°C
Records	annual
From	1950
To	2044
Years	95
Baseline (BL)	1850-1900
BL years	51
Ave in BL	N/A
Decimal places	6

Chart 6 - DB16 – IPCC dataset - Global Warming (Land+Ocean) 1950-2014, °C above pBL [8]

All Datasets for GW (Land+Ocean)

Chart 7 - All datasets - Global Warming (Land+Ocean) 1850-2024, °C above pBL

Chart 8 - DB17 Average dataset - Global Warming (Land+Ocean) 1850-2024, °C above pBL

Average Dataset (DB17) 1-2024 for GW (Land+Ocean)

The average dataset is based on the following datasets:

- Paleo DB11
- Thermo DB12
- NASA DB13
- NOAA DB14
- LBL DB15
- IPCC DB16

Chart 9 - DB17 Average dataset - Global Warming (Land+Ocean) 1-2024, °C above pBL

Chart 10 - DB17 Average dataset – 31 years moving average

The red line is related to the center of the moving average, for instance, the average of the data between 1985 and 2015 is indicated in the year 2000.

Global Warming over Land GWL Datasets

Table 9 - Global Warming over Land only GWL datasets considered in this work

	Ref	ID	1750-1850	1850-1880	1880-2024
NASA	[3] [4]	DB21			
NOAA	[5]	DB22			
LBL	[6] [7]	DB23			
LBL miniAmp	*	DB24			
Ave	*	DB25			

* this publication

NASA Database (DB21) 1880-2024 for GWL (Land only)

Table 10 - DB21 - NASA GWL Database info [3] [4]

DB21	NASA
Name	NASA
ID	DB21
Reference	[3] [4]
Units	°C
Records	annual
From	1880
To	2024
Years	145
Baseline (BL)	1951-1980
BL years	30
Ave in BL	0.0003
Decimal places	2
CF(pBL)	+0.4428

Chart 11 - DB21 - NASA dataset - GWL (Land only) 1880-2024, °C above pBL [3] [4]

NOAA Database (DB22) 1850-2024 for GWL (Land only)Table 11 - DB22 - NOAA GWL Database info [5]

DB22	NOAA
Name	NOAA
ID	DB22
Reference	[5]
Units	°C
Records	annual
From	1850
To	2024
Years	175
Baseline (BL)	1901-2000
BL years	100
Ave in BL	0.0000
Decimal places	2
CF(pBL)	+0.4512

Chart 12 - DB22 - NOAA dataset - GWL (Land only) 1850-2024, °C above pBL [5]

Berkley Earth Database (DB23) 1750-2024 for GWL (Land only)Table 12 - DB23 - LBL GWL Database info [6] [7]

DB23	Berkley Earth
Name	LBL
ID	DB23
Reference	[6] [7]
Units	°C
Records	annual
From	1750
To	2024
Years	275
Baseline (BL)	1951-1980
BL years	30
Ave in BL	0.0000
Decimal places	3
CF(pBL)	+0.4540

Chart 13 - DB23 - LBL dataset - GWL (Land only) 1750-2024, °C above pBL [6] [7]

LBL miniAmp Dataset (DB24) 1750-2024 for GWL (Land only)

The above chart of DB23 has very big amplitude in the 1750-1878 period.

The 1880-1930 period has much smaller amplitude.

The correction procedure will uniformly decrease the amplitude in the 1750-1880 period by the ratio of the average amplitudes in both periods.

Table 13 - Cubic trendline of DB23 in 1750-1930

Table 14 - Cubic trendline of DB23 in 1750-1930 period

a	0.000000226114691	x ³
b	-0.000056055010124	x ²
c	0.006262266395394	x
d	-0.422224482223104	
Start	1749	

Table 15 - Average amplitudes in 1750-1880 and 1880-1930 periods

Period	Max Amp	Ave Amp	Max/Ave
Before correction			
1750-1880	1.615	0.380	4.2
1880-1930	0.344	0.129	2.7
Period2/Period1	0.213	0.339	
After correction			
1750-1880	0.547	0.129	4.2

Chart 14 - miniAmp - reduced amplitude of LBL dataset in 1750-1880 - GWL (Land only) °C above pBL [6] [7]

Chart 15 - DB24 - LBL miniAmp dataset - GWL (Land only) 1750-2024, °C above pBL

All Datasets for GWL (Land only)

Chart 16 - All datasets - GWL (Land only) 1750-2024, °C above pBL

The similarity of all the datasets in the 1880-2024 period is quite impressive indicating also the correctness of baseline conversion factors.

Average Dataset (DB25) 1750-2024 for GWL (Land only)

The average dataset is based on the following datasets:

- NASA DB21
- NOAA DB22
- LBL miniAmp DB24

Chart 17 - DB25 Average dataset - GWL (Land only) cubic trendline 1750-2024, °C above pBL

Chart 18 - DB25 Average dataset - GWL (Land only) moving average 31 years, °C above pBL

Global Warming over the Ocean GWO Datasets

Table 16 - Global Warming over the Land only GWO datasets considered in this work

	Ref	ID	1750-1850	1850-1880	1880-2024
NASA	[3] [4]	DB31			
NOAA	[5]	DB32			
DB33	DB1+DB24	DB33			
Ave	*	DB34			

* this publication

NASA Database (DB31) 1880-2024 for GWO (Ocean only)

Table 17 - DB31 - NASA GWO Database info [3] [4]

DB31	NASA
Name	NASA
ID	DB31
Reference	[3] [4]
Units	°C
Records	annual
From	1880
To	2024
Years	145
Baseline (BL)	1951-1980
BL years	30
Ave in BL	0.0007
Decimal places	2
CF(pBL)	+0.0981

Chart 19 - DB31 - NASA dataset - GWO (Ocean only) 1880-2024, °C above pBL
[3] [4]

NOAA Database (DB32) 1850-2024 for GWO (Ocean only)

Table 18 - DB32 - NOAA GWO Database info [5]

DB32	NOAA
Name	NOAA
ID	DB32
Reference	[5]
Units	°C
Records	annual
From	1850
To	2024
Years	175
Baseline (BL)	1901-2000
BL years	100
Ave in BL	0.0000
Decimal places	2
CF(pBL)	+0.0441

Chart 20 - DB32 - NOAA dataset - GWO (Ocean only) 1850-2024, °C above pBL [5]

Global Warming over the Ocean in 1750-1850 (DB33)

Publication [9] includes formula for calculation of GW using GWL and GWO according to land and ocean area.

Formula 1 - Calculation of GW using GWL and GWO according to land and ocean area [9]

$$\mathbf{GW = GWL*AL + GWO*AO}$$

GW	Global Warming, global surface temperature above the 1850-1900 baseline, land+ocean, °C
GWL	global surface temperature over the land only above the 1850-1900 baseline, °C
GWO	global surface temperature over the ocean only, above the 1850-1900 baseline, °C
AL	global area of land, %
AO	global area of the ocean, %

AL and AO are determined in the publication [9] as follows:

Based on the Global Warming data, the average land area (AL) in the period 1990-2021 was 31.18% of the total area of the Earth, and the ocean area (AO) was 68.82%.

Table 19 - Land area and ocean area [9]

Global Land Area	AL	31.18%
Global Ocean Area	AO	68.82%

The current publication includes data of GW and GWL for 1750-1850, which allows calculations of GWO in this period applying Formula 1.

$$\mathbf{GWO = (GW - GWL*AL) / AO}$$

Table 20 - Datasets applied for DB33 calculations

	GW	GWL
Name	Paleo	miniAmp
ID	DB11	DB24
Ref	[1] [2]	*
BL	1850-1900	1850-1900

*this publication

Chart 21 - DB33 dataset - GWO (Ocean only) 1750-1850 calculated with Formula 1, °C above pBL

All Datasets for GWO (Ocean only)

Chart 22 - All datasets - GWO (Ocean only) 1750-2024, °C above pBL

Like the GWL datasets, the GWO datasets show impressive similarity indicating also the correctness of baseline conversion factors.

Average Dataset (DB34) 1750-2024 for GWO (Ocean only)

The average dataset includes the following datasets:

- NASA DB31
- NOAA DB32
- DB33 calculated with Formula 1 based on DB11 (Paleo) and DB24 (miniAmp)

Chart 23 - DB34 Average dataset - GWO (Ocean only) cubic trendline 1750-2024, °C above pBL

Chart 24 - DB34 Average dataset - GWO (Ocean only) moving average 31 years, °C above pBL

Datasets GW, GWL, GWO

Chart 25 - GW, GWL, GWO, °C above pBL

Chart 26 - Difference between GWL and GW 1750-2024, °C

The linear and the cubic trendline show that the difference between GWL and GW increases constantly, from -0.40°C in 1750 to +0.47°C in 2024, 0.00316°C per year.

Availability of the GW, GWL, GWO datasets

GW, GWL, GWO datasets according to this work are publically available online on site nowagreen.com

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